

HELICOPEVRA ZEA HASHAROT HUYAYRALARINI KO`PAYTIRISH UCHUN OPTIMAL SHAROITLARINI TANLASH

**S.Gaynazarova, I.Ko`paysinova, Sh.Hasanov, J.Abdurahmanov,
S.Sasmakov, Sh.Azimova**

O`zR FA akad. S.Yu.Yunusov nomidagi O`simlik moddalari kimyosi instituti.

genlab_icps@yahoo.com

O`zbekiston.

Helicopevra zea (Amerika makkajo`xori sofkasi) hasharot hujayralari, bakulovirus hasharot hujayralariga asoslangan tadqiqot ishlarida muhim o`rin tutadi. Helicopevra zea asosiy qishloq xo`jaligi zararkunandsi hisoblanadi. Asosan makkajo`xori, pamidor va bir qancha poliz ekinlarini zararlaydi. Lichinkalik davrida turli xil o`simlik hujayralari bilan oziqlangan. Bu tur Shimoliy Kanada, Alyaska va Amerikada keng tarqalgan [1-3].

Bugungi kunda, bakulovirus hasharot hujayralaridan biotexnologiya va farmatsevtika sanoatida keng foydalanilmoqda. Chunki, boshqa ekspressiya tizimlari orasida ya`ni sutemizuvchi hamda achitqi hujayralari bilan taqqoslaganda, hasharot hujayralari oson rivojlanadi va o`sinh tezligi yuqoridir [4-5].

So`nggi yilliklarda dunyo aholisining izchil o`sishi qishloq xo`jalik mahsulotlariga bo`lgan talabni yanada oshirmoqda. Bu esa o`z navbatida qishloq xo`jalik ekinlarini to`g`ri parvarish qilish hamda turli zararkunanda hasharotlardan himoya qilishni talab qilmoqda. Insektitsid vositalar zararkunandalarga qarshi kurashish uchun eng samarali vositalardan biridir. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko`ra, insektitsidlar hosilning 94% gacha saqlab qolinishiga yordam beradi. Shunday qilib, qishloq xo`jalik o`simliklari zararkunandalarga qarshi kurash uchun yangi insektitsidlarni ishlab chiqish ayni paytda hal qilinishi kerak bo`lgan muammolardan biridi. Hozirda hasharot hujayralar ustida turli xil sintetik va biologik faol moddalarni insektitsid faolligini in vitro tadqiq qilish orqali yangi avlod insektitsid vositalarini tez va oson topish imkonini bermoqda. Natijada aktivlik ko`rsatgan moddalar qishloq xo`jaligi zararkunandalarga qarshi vosita sifatida qo`llanilishi mumkin [6-7].

Yuqoridagilarni inobatga olib Helicopevra zea hasharot hujayralarini ko`paytirish usullarini optimallashtirish orqali ular ustida turli xil tadqiqotlar olib borish imkonini beradi.

Hasharot hujayralariga mo`ljallangan ozuqa muhitlar murakkab bo`lib, uglevodlar, tuzlar, aminokislotalar, o`sinh omillari, vitaminlar, gormonlar va

mikroelementlardan iborat. Ushbu tarkibiy qismlardan hujayra turlariga nisbatan turlicha foydalanishimiz mumkin.

Tadqiqotimizni ilmiy adabiyotlarda keltirilgan ma'lumotlardan foydalangan holda, *Helicoverpa zea* hujayrasi uchun 5% dan 20% gacha embrion zardobi (Gibco™ Fetal Bovine Serum) saqlovchi Grace's (Gibco™) ozuqa muhitida +18°C dan +26 °C gacha harorat ostida 7 kun davomida o'stirishdan boshladik [8]. Tajribalar natijasiga ko'ra tarkibida 15% zardob saqlovchi ozuqa muhiti va +22°C harorat, shuningdek 10% zardob saqlovchi ozuqa muhiti va +26°C harorat ostida hujayra liniyalarini ko'paytirish eng optimal sharoitlar ekani ko'rsatib berildi va nisbatan qimmat turadigan FBS reagentining tejalishiga erishildi.

Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra *Helicoverpa zea* hasharot hujayra liniyasini laboratoriya sharoitida ko'paytirishning maqbul sharoitlari tanlab olindi. Mazkur sharoitlar tabiiy va sintetik moddalarning insektitsid faolligini o'rganishga keng imkoniyat ochib beradi.

REFERENCES

1. Lambert B, Buysse L, Decock C, Jansens S, Piens C, Saey B, et al. (January 1996). "A *Bacillus thuringiensis* insecticidal crystal protein with a high activity against members of the family Noctuidae". *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 62 (1): 80–6. Bibcode: 1996ApEnM..62.80L. doi:10.1128/AEM.62.1.80-86.1996
2. Light DM, Flath RA, Buttery RG, Zalom FG, Rice RE, Dickens JC, Jang EB (September 1993). "Host-plant green-leaf volatiles synergize the synthetic sex pheromones of the corn earworm and codling moth (Lepidoptera)". *Chemoecology*. 4 (3–4): 145–52. doi:10.1007/BF01256549. S2CID 21610251.
3. Mau RF, Kessing JL. "*Helicoverpa zea* (Boddie)". *Crop Knowledge Master*. Department of Entomology, University of Hawaii.
4. Ikonomou L, Schneider YJ, Agathos SN. Insect cell culture for industrial production of recombinant proteins // *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*. 2003, 62: 1-20. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12733003>
5. Murakami K, Uchiyama A, Kokuho T, Mori Y, Sentsui H, et al. Production of biologically active recombinant bovine interferon-g by two different baculovirus gene expression system using insect cells and silkworm larvae // *Cytokine* 2001, 13: 18-24. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11145838>
6. Ahmad M., Saeed F., Noor Jahan M. Evaluation of Insecticidal and Anti-oxidant activity of Selected Medicinal Plants // *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2013, 2 (3): 153-158.

7. Singh T., Kumar V.R., Bhavani N.L., Pravallika D., Roja K. and Pravallika V. In vitro insecticidal activity of Solanum melongena // European journal of pharmaceutical and medical research. 2016, 3(5): 420-422.
8. Grace's insect cell culture medium, supplemented instructions for use. Doc ID: 179405 Rev. No.:2. ©2016 Expression Systems LLC.